

Heterocyclic Systems Containing Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom. Part—XLVII. Syntheses of Thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazoline and Thiazino[2,3-*b*]quinazoline

G. D. GUPTA and H. K. PUJARI*

† Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

2-Mercapto-8-methyl-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (2a), obtained by the reaction of 3-methylantranilic acid (1) with ammonium thiocyanate, on condensation with chloroacetic acid gives the acid (3a) which on treatment with acetic anhydride and pyridine undergoes cyclodehydration to furnish a single product to which 9-methyl-2*H*-thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-3,5-dione (4a) and not 5-methyl-2*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]quinazolin-3,9-dione (7a) was assigned on the basis of pmr spectral data. Similarly, (2a) on condensation with 1,2-dibromoethane and 1,3-dibromopropane yields 2,3-dihydro-9-methylthiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-5-one (5a) and 4*H*-2,3-dihydro-10-methyl[1,3]thiazino[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-6-one (6), respectively.

KENDALL and Duffin¹ reported in a British patent that the cyclisation of 3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one-2-thiolacetic acid (3b), obtained by the reaction of 2-mercapto-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (2b) with chloroacetic acid, yielded a cyclised product which may be represented by either 2*H*-thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-3,5-dione (4b) or 2*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]quinazolin-3,9-dione (7b). They, however, did not characterise the cyclised product. Dhatt and Narang² repeated the above work and found that the acid (3a) on heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine underwent decomposition.

2-Mercapto-8-methyl-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (2a), prepared by the condensation of 3-methylantranilic acid (1) with ammonium thiocyanate following the method of Frank and Smith³ for the synthesis of phenylthiourea, when reacted with chloroacetic acid gave 8-methyl-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one-2-thiolacetic acid (3a). The acid (3a), being unsymmetrical, on cyclisation was expected to give 9-methyl-2*H*-thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-3,5-dione (4a) or 5-methyl-2*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]quinazolin-3,9-dione (7a) or both depending upon the mode of cyclisation. The acid (3a), however, on treatment with acetic anhydride underwent cyclodehydration furnishing a single product (tlc). The absorption of carbonyl groups at 1680 and 1775 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectrum of the cyclised product though supported the cyclic nature of the product yet could not decide firmly the presence or absence of -CO-N-CO group⁴. The molecular ion peak (M⁺) at *m/z* 232 exhibited in the mass spectrum of the tlc-pure product supported the molecular formula, thus corroborating the cyclisation product. However, the structure, 9-methyl-2*H*-thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-3,5-dione (4a) was finally assigned to this cyclisation product in preference to the structure, 5-methyl-2*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]quinazolin-3,9-dione (7a) on the basis of pmr spectral studies.

The reaction of 2-mercapto-8-methyl-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (2a) with 1,2-dibromoethane also gave a tlc-pure single product which could be represented either by the structure 9-methyl-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-5-one (5a) or 5-methyl-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[3,2-*a*]quinazolin-9-one (8a). The exhibition of the molecular ion peak (M⁺) at *m/z* 218 in the mass spectrum of this tlc-pure product supports the cyclisation product 5a or 8a. In either structure, the signal at δ 2.18 was assignable to methyl protons. The appearance of methyl signal at δ 2.20 (which is almost of the same

a, R=CH₃,
b, R=H
(1). H₂NBCN, BrCl, (2). ClCH₂CO₂H; (3). Ac₂O, pyridine;
(4). BrCH₂CH₂Br; (5). BrCH₂CH₂CH₂Br.

value as 2.18) in the pmr spectrum of the cyclisation product obtained from **3a** led to the assignment of the structure **4a** for the cyclisation product. Where the structure **7a** correct, then the methyl protons would have shown a downfield shift due to the deshielding effect of carbonyl group of thiazolidinone ring. The magnetic anisotropic effect of a similar carbonyl group has been found to deshield the *peri*-methyl protons⁸ to an appreciable extent.

Howard and Klein⁶ obtained 2,3-dihydrothiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-5-one (**5b**) by the reaction of **2b** with 1,2-dibromoethane, while the reaction of ethyl-*N*-thiocarbamoylanthranilate with 1,2-dibromoethane yielded 2,3-dihydrothiazolo[3,2-*a*]quinazolin-9-one (**8b**) although structure **5b** was assigned to this product earlier by Narang *et al.*⁷ The structure **5** was assigned to the tlc-pure cyclisation product obtained from the reaction of **2b** with 1,2-dibromoethane on the analogy with the structure **4** as well as the work of Howard and Klein⁶.

Similarly, the reaction of **2a** with 1,3-dibromopropane gave a tlc-pure single product to which the structure 10-methyl-4H-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazino[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-6-one (**6**) and not **9** was assigned on analogy with the structure **4a** although the pmr data (*vide* experimental) and the exhibition of molecular ion peak (M^+) at m/z 232 corroborate the cyclisation product.

Fungicidal test: For fungicidal assay, the method of Aytoun *et al.*⁹ was used. *Aspergillus flavus*, *Candida albicans*, *Microsporium gypseum* and *Nocardia asteroidis* were used as test fungi. The thiazolidinone (**4a**) was found to be active against all the fungi at 1 : 500 dilution.

Bactericidal test: The Riedel-Walker⁹ serial drop dilution method was used for comparative antibacterial activity using 24 h old culture of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. Here also only the thiazolidinone was found to be active against both the bacteria at 1 : 500 dilution.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. Tlc was performed on silica gel plates using acetone-benzene (1 : 3) as the solvent system. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were run on Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference. Mass spectra were scanned on Hitachi RMU-6 spectrometer.

3-Methylantranilic acid (1): It was prepared in 60% yield from 7-methylsatin following the method of Baker *et al.*¹⁰ for the synthesis of 3-chloroanthranilic acid, m.p. 172° (lit.^{11,12} 172°).

8-Methyl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (2a): 3-Methylantranilic acid (**1**; 7.55 g, 0.05 mol) was heated with ammoniumthiocyanate (4.56 g, 0.06 mol) following Frank and Smith³ synthesis for phenylthiourea to give 8-methyl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (55%, m.p. 262° (aq. DMF)

(Found: S, 16.52; N, 14.26. $C_9H_8N_2SO$ requires S, 16.67; N, 14.58%); ν_{max} 1150 (C=S), 1550 (C-N), 1610 (C=N), 1675 (C=O), 3100 cm^{-1} (N-H).

8-Methyl-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one-2-thiolacetic acid (3a): 8-Methyl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (**2a**; 1.92 g, 0.01 mol) in DMF-NaOH (1.5 g of NaOH in a mixture of 15 ml DMF and 10 ml of water) was added to a mixture of chloroacetic acid (2.58 g, 0.03 mol) in sodium carbonate solution (3.0 g of Na_2CO_3 dissolved in a mixture of 10 ml DMF and 15 ml water) and the reaction mixture was heated on steam bath for 3 h. The suspended impurities were removed by filtration, the filtrate poured into water (50 ml) and then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The white solid, thus separated, was filtered, washed well with water and crystallised from ethanol as white flakes (1.7 g, 68%), m.p. 240 (d) (Found: S, 13.20; N, 11.34. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2SO_2$ requires S, 12.80; N, 11.20%); ν_{max} 1600, 1635 (C=N and C=C), 1690 (C=O), 2580-2700 cm^{-1} (COOH).

9-Methyl-2H-thiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-3,5-dione (4a): A mixture of **3a** (1.0 g), acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (3 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 20 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into water. The solid, thus obtained, was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and finally crystallised from aq. DMF as light brown flakes (0.4 g, 43%), m.p. 212° (Found: S, 13.92; N, 11.92, M^+ at m/z 232. $C_{11}H_8N_2SO_2$ requires S, 13.79; N, 12.07%, mol.wt. 232); ν_{max} 1590 (C=N), 1680, 1775 cm^{-1} (both carbonyl groups in O=C-N-C=O); δ (TFA) 2.20 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.06 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.08-7.82 (3H, m, Ar-H).

9-Methyl-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-5-one (5a): A solution of 8-methyl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (**2a**; 0.96 g, 0.005 mol) in 60% aq. isopropanol (25 ml) containing sodium hydroxide (0.2 g) and sodium carbonate (1.75 g) was added in small lots to a refluxing solution of 1,2-dibromoethane (2 ml in 10 ml of isopropanol) and refluxing was continued for 4 h. Isopropanol was distilled off and the solid, thus obtained, was filtered, washed well with water and finally crystallised from ethanol giving cream coloured needles (0.70 g, 64%), m.p. 164-65° (Found: S, 14.35; N, 12.52, M^+ at m/z 218. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2SO$ requires S, 14.68; N, 12.84%, mol. wt. 218); ν_{max} 1580, 1600 (C=C and C=N), 1675 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (TFA) 2.18 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.49 (2H, t, SCH_2), 4.46 (2H, t, NCH_2), 7.07-7.77 (3H, m, Ar-H).

10-Methyl-4H-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazino[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-6-one (6a): To a refluxing solution of 1,3-dibromopropane (2 ml in 10 ml isopropanol) was added in small lots, a solution of 8-methyl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-4-one (**2a**; 0.96 g, 0.005 mol) in 60% aqueous isopropanol (25 ml) containing sodium hydroxide (0.2 g) and sodium bicarbonate (1.75 g) and refluxing continued for 4 h. Isopropanol was distilled off and the aqueous

solution left behind was allowed to stand overnight. The solid, thus obtained, was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and finally crystallised from ethanol to give 10-methyl-4*H*-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazino[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-6-one as light brown needles (0.6 g, 52%), m.p. 135° (Found : S, 13.62 ; N, 12.24, M⁺ at *m/z* 232. C₁₂H₁₂N₂SO requires S, 13.79 ; N, 12.07%, mol. wt. 232); $\nu_{\max}$ 1540 (C-N stretching), 1590, 1610 (C=N and C=C), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (TFA) 2.33-2.69 (5H, m, CH₂ and SCH₂CH₂CH₂N), 3.48 (2H, t, SCH₂), 4.36 (2H, t, NCH₂), 7.48-7.83 (2H, m, H₈ and H₉) and 8.18 (1H, d, each broad, H₇, *J*_{7,8} 8 Hz).

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